

Research the Impact of Green Logistics Practices on the Sustainable Performance of Small and Medium-Sized Logistics Enterprises in Hanoi

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Abstract:

Research to understand the impact of green Logistics practices on the sustainable efficiency of businesses, focusing on small and medium-sized Logistics enterprises in Hanoi. Research results show that the sustainable efficiency of Logistics enterprises is influenced by 4 important factors in green Logistics practices: reverse Logistics practices, carbon emission management, green fuel usage practices and green transportation practices. From there, the authors propose some management implications to help Logistics service providers improve green Logistics practices and towards sustainability.

Keywords:

Green Logistics practices, Sustainable efficiency, Logistics enterprises, Hanoi

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the world economy has developed strongly, but this also directly impacts the environment, causing climate change. Many say the world is facing a natural resource crisis worse than the financial crisis. A 2012 Living Planet report calculated humans are using 30 percent more resources than Earth can replenish each year, leading to deforestation, land degradation, polluted air and water, and severe declines in the numbers of fish and other species. Logistics is considered one of the main causes of negative impacts on the environment such as carbon emissions. This evidence shows that the Logistics industry is responsible for greenhouse gas emissions from transport activities, especially caused by freight. Therefore, implementing green Logistics activities is an inevitable and urgent trend.

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Currently, consumers care a lot about environmental issues, they want to use green services. In addition, environmental regulations and improving corporate social responsibility are increasingly tightening. Therefore, it is important for Logistics companies to consider how the services they provide affect people and the environment. This has undoubtedly forced companies to incorporate green Logistics practices in their Logistics activities to provide green services that are more environmentally friendly and responsible for environmental sustainability, thereby enhancing competitiveness as well as towards sustainable effective development. However, Green Logistics in Vietnam is still at the development stage. Therefore, the authors carried out the research topic: "Research the impact of green Logistics practices on the sustainable efficiency of small and medium-sized Logistics enterprises in Hanoi". This study is an important step in understanding and promoting sustainable development in the Logistics industry. Theoretically, the research contributes to adding to the literature on Green Logistics, Green Logistics practices, Reverse Logistics, Green fuel, Green transportation, Carbon emission management and Sustainable efficiency of logistics enterprises. In terms of application, the research findings will help logistics service providers improve green logistics practices, minimize the impact of the logistics industry on the environment, and aim for long-term sustainability.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1. Green Logistics and green Logistics practices.

According to (Rodrigue, 2012), the term "green logistics" is defined as supply chain management practices and strategies that reduce the environmental and energy footprint of freight distribution, which focuses on material handling, waste management, packaging and transport. (S. Y. Lee & Klassen, 2008) describe green logistics as Green Supply Chain Management that can be defined as an organizations activity taking into account environmental issues and integrating it into supply chain management in order to change the environmental performance of suppliers and customers, while according to (Sbihi & Eglese, 2009), green logistics activities include measuring the environmental impact of different distribution strategies, reducing the energy usage in logistics

activities, reducing waste and managing its treatment. From the sustainable development point of view, green logistics can be defined as, “producing and distributing goods in a sustainable way, taking account of environmental and social factors” (Sbihi & Eglese, 2009).

Green Logistics practices include a set of green activities that help minimize the overall environmental impact of Logistics activities and ensure the protection and sustainable development of the natural, social and corporate environment (Agyabeng-Mensah, 2020).

2.2. Reverse Logistics practices

According to Pokharel và Mutha (2009), reverse Logistics practices include two main activities: product recovery, reuse, and waste treatment. Reverse logistics is a comprehensive process that involves planning, implementing, and controlling the reverse flow of materials in general such as raw materials, finished goods, work in progress, packaging, and information (Rogers & Tibben-Lembke, 1999). Reverse logistics processes surplus with the aim of creating an economical and environmentally friendly flow of surplus by using both spatial and temporal transformation activities that include changing volume and type (Doan Thi Hong Anh, 2020). Therefore, reverse Logistics activities will contribute to environmental protection and bring many benefits to the sustainable efficiency of businesses.

2.3. Carbon Emission Management

The impact of carbon emissions creeps into every corner of social life, profoundly affecting population growth, the job market, health systems, food security and energy security (Duong, & cs, 2018). According to the IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change), Carbon emission management is a set of methods and policies aimed at reducing the amount of greenhouse gases (GHGs) released into the environment, especially CO₂. The main goal is to mitigate the effects of climate change and protect the environment. Besides, Rehman et al. (2021) also states that carbon emission management is the process of reducing the amount of carbon dioxide (CO₂) produced and released into the atmosphere. It involves a series of activities aimed at reducing the

amount of CO₂ from sources such as power plants, industrial facilities and transportation, as well as increasing the amount of carbon stored or removed from the atmosphere through activities such as afforestation and carbon capture and storage..

2.4. Green fuel usage practices

Green fuel usage practices is reflected in the use of less polluting or non-polluting fuel sources (Research on Green Logistics development at home and abroad, Guoyi Xiu, Xiaohua Chen, 2012). Enterprises increase the use of renewable or alternative energy sources in transportation, warehousing, packaging, information technology application during operation, helping to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, especially CO₂ from Logistics activities, environmental protection and climate change response, promote economic and social development.

2.5. Green Transportation Practices

Green transportation practices refer to the efficient use of energy resources for the transportation of passengers and goods, protecting the global environment from greenhouse gases and environmental pollutants (The Asian Journal of Transportation and Logistics, 2017).

2.6. Sustainable efficiency of enterprise

Sustainable efficiency of enterprise is defined as the ability of companies to reduce harmful emissions and improve financial efficiency to maintain a long-term competitive advantage (Xie & Zhu, 2020), while also including the ability to consume resources efficiently and commit to providing better ethical services to meet society's needs (Khoa & Anh, 2021).

3. HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

3.1. The relationship between reverse Logistics practices and sustainable efficiency of enterprise

Reverse Logistics has become an important competency of modern supply chains because of its importance in recovering products and managing their handling. Geng et

al. demonstrated that reverse Logistics has a moderate overall impact on three activities: economic, environmental, and social.

Reverse Logistics practices contribute significantly to improving the sustainable efficiency of Logistics service providers, such as through its impact on cost savings (Jack et al., 2010); improve customer satisfaction by acting socially and environmentally responsible (Glenn Richey et al., 2005; Li and Olorunniwo, 2008); improve customer loyalty by paying more attention to defective products (Aitken and Harrison, 2013); and its positive impact on climate change and global warming by taking back products and reducing their carbon footprint (Carter & Rogers, 2008).

Based on these arguments, the authors propose the following hypothesis:

"H1: Reverse Logistics practices have a positive effect on the sustainable efficiency of enterprise."

3.2. The relationship between carbon emission management and sustainable efficiency of enterprise

Carbon emissions have posed serious challenges to global sustainable development by causing climate change on a global scale (Song, Zhou, & Liu, 2018). The impact of carbon emissions creeps into every corner of social life, deeply affecting population growth, the job market, the health system, food security and energy security. While transitioning to a low-carbon economy and climate change regulations may bring new job opportunities, they also pose a potential risk of increasing poverty in society (Li, Zhang, & Zhang, 2023). However, because the development of clean energy and renewable energy technology requires higher skills and qualifications from workers, this leads to the risk of narrowing job opportunities in the energy sectors. traditional energy, potentially causing social instability (Mazlan et al., 2020). In terms of health, reducing carbon emissions can improve air quality, improve public health, and reduce the burden on the healthcare system (Farooq, Shahzad, Sarwar, & ZaiJun, 2019). Regarding food security, global warming affects agricultural production in various ways such as rainfall, temperature and carbon emissions, seriously threatening food security (Rehman et al., 2021). In the field of energy security, actively promoting renewable energy is an

essential measure to reduce carbon emissions. By promoting the use of renewable energy and improving energy efficiency, it is possible to reduce energy dependence on foreign oil and increase the flexibility of the energy system to enhance energy security. quantity. Therefore, developing a carbon management system is one of the important mechanisms to achieve green economic growth, social welfare and development as well as environmental protection and management (C. T. Lee, Hashim, Ho, Van Fan, & Klemeš, 2017)

Based on these arguments, the authors propose the following hypothesis:

“H2: Carbon emission management has a positive effect on the sustainable efficiency of enterprise.”

3.3. The relationship between green fuel usage practices and sustainable efficiency of enterprise

Green fuel usage practices plays an important role and is closely related to the sustainable efficiency of businesses. The friendliness of fuels meets the potential of greening Logistics, satisfying the need for greening in each stage. In transportation, using fuels to replace fossil fuels also helps significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Studying Logistics activities in the UK (UKWA, 2010), researchers pointed out that 3% of emissions come from Logistics activities and about 4% from freight transportation activities using fossil fuels. Besides, the world is also facing the extremely serious problem of plastic waste pollution. According to statistics, each year the world generates about 200 million tons of plastic waste mixed with household solid waste (Dalberg Advisors, 2021(Dinh Khoa & Mai Anh, 2023)). The practice of Green Logistics, specifically the practice of using green fuel, allows businesses to take a responsible approach to the environment (Dinh Khoa & Mai Anh, 2023). This is not only a way to meet customers' environmental requirements, but also a guarantee of the business towards the environment, building a responsible image of the business towards the environment, thereby increasing the level of satisfaction, contributing to business economic development towards sustainable, long-term efficiency.

Based on these arguments, the authors propose the following hypothesis:

“H3: Green fuel usage practices has a positive effect on the sustainable efficiency of businesses.”

3.4. The relationship between green transportation practices and corporate sustainability efficiency

Collaboration in freight transport systems (Takaoka et al., 2000) allows reducing the number of trucks used to collect or transport the same amount of items. This results in a significant reduction in truck travel time, man hours and overall costs.

Changing vehicles, optimizing routes during transportation, or combining multi-modal transportation or introducing packaging standards and specifications to optimize transportation based on the vehicle's carrying capacity and digital transformation techniques in transportation, which help reduce energy use and cause greenhouse gas emissions, are an important potential in green Logistics practices that businesses should apply and implement well. Green transportation will help businesses develop long-term and sustainably (Karagülle, 2012)

Based on these arguments, the authors propose the following hypothesis:

“H4: Green transportation practices has a positive effect on the sustainable efficiency of enterprise.”

4. RESEARCH METHODS AND RESEARCH MODELS

4.1. Research method

4.1.1. Qualitative research

Through referring to research documents and consulting with experts, the initial research model is based on the research model of Noorliza Karia (2020), related research works. important domestic and foreign issues and propose some observations to measure reverse Logistics practices, carbon emission management, green fuel usage practices, and green transportation practices. The sustainable efficiency of enterprises is measured by the scales proposed by the author (Basiago, 1998).

4.1.2. Questionnaire design

Results of scale measuring green Logistics practices to sustainable efficiency of enterprises after being adjusted to suit reality including 04 independent variables: (1)

Reverse Logistics practices; (2) Carbon emission management; (3) Green fuel usage practices; (4) Green transportation practices. With 20 observed variables and 06 business information (business name, position in the business, number of members, Logistics services that the business is providing). All observed variables in the components are used a 5-level Likert scale with corresponding levels: level 1 - strongly disagree, level 2 - disagree, level 3 - undecided, level 4 - agree and level 5 - strongly agree. The official measurement scale and observed variables are shown in detail as follows:

Variable name	Observation (Scale)	Symbol	Quote source
Reverse Logistics practices	The reverse Logistics process is implemented quickly and promptly by the enterprise	LN1	(Fleischmann & Baah, 2001)
	Recall information is continuously and clearly updated by the enterprise	LN2	(Mohr & Spekman, 1994)
	The enterprise has a system to recall products and packaging	LN3	(Agyabeng-Mensah, 2020), (Baah, Jin, & Tang, 2020)
	The enterprise has a system handling packaging and waste	LN4	(Đoàn Thị Hồng Anh, 2020)
Carbon Emission Management	Enterprises update knowledge about timely carbon reduction	CB1	(Hawken, 2016)
	Enterprises apply carbon emissions management measures	CB2	(McKinnon, 2010), (De Baker, Gebruers, & Delcour, 2009)
	Government supports businesses in a timely manner in the transformation of green energy	CB3	(Wolf & Seuring, 2010)
	Enterprises using renewable energy	LX1	(Đoàn Thị Hồng Anh, 2020); (Meneghetti & Monti, 2014)

Green fuel usage practices	Enterprises using environmentally friendly equipment and vehicles	LX2	(Cordeiro & Sarkis, 1997), (Meneghetti & Monti, 2014)
	Enterprises using packaging made from materials that can be recycled and reused	LX3	(Rao, 2005), (Holt & Ghobadian, 2009), (Paulraj & Environment, 2009), and (Vachon, 2007)
	Enterprises making efforts to reduce energy consumption packaging materials	LX4	
Green transportation practices	Enterprises promote standardization of transportation operations	CX1	(Zhang & Choi, 2014)
	Enterprises route planning and freight consolidation	CX2	(Soliman & Noorliza, 2020)
	Enterprises tend to choose greener vehicles and greener modes of transportation such as shipping by sea and by air	CX3	(Zhang & Choi, 2014)
Sustainable efficiency	Profit on revenue increased significantly through green Logistics practices	BV1	(Beullens, Van Wassenhove, Van Oudheusden, & Cattrysse, 1999), (Wanger et al., 2005); (Zeng & Veeravalli, 2010)
	Green Logistics practices help businesses grow market share	BV2	(Pawar, 2021)
	Green Logistics practices help protect the environment, reduce greenhouse emissions	BV3	(SZYMANSKI*, 2004); (Zhu & Sarkis, 2004)
	Green Logistics practices help save energy and resources	BV4	(Kim, 2017) (Kool, 2016)
	Green Logistics practices help improve community health and safety	BV5	(Han & Huo, 2020)
	Green Logistics practices help reduce environmental impact on the public	BV6	

Table 1. Observed variables in the research model

4.1.3. Quantitative research

Sample size depends on the analytical method (Gorsuch & Venable, 1983). According to the rule of thumb (Nguyễn Đình Thọ, 2011), the number of observations is (at least) 5 times greater than the number of observed variables. Thus, with 20 observed variables, the study needs a minimum sample size of 100.

The authors collected data using a questionnaire designed on Google Form. The authors used convenience sampling method. After the period from January 8, 2024 to April 10, 2024, the author group received 135 votes. However, after screening, 3 votes were eliminated due to duplicate data. The final number of votes included in the analysis was 132 votes.

4.2. Proposed research model

Figure 1. Research model of the topic

5. RESEARCH RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

5.1. Research results

5.1.1 Descriptive statistics

Elements		Frequency (%)
Labor size of the enterprise	< 50	60.3
	50-200	39.7
Target market	Domestic	100
	Foreign	28.03
Business field	Shipping services	90.9
	Customs declaration service	76.5
	Warehousing services	62.9
	Freight Forwarding	56.8
	Other	19.7

Table 2. Results of business information survey

The survey results are presented specifically in Table 4.1

5.1.2 Test scale reliability using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient

The results of the analysis indicate that the Cronbach's Alpha coefficients are all greater than 0.6. The Corrected Item-Total Correlation coefficients of the observed variables are all > 0.3, indicating that the research concepts constructed from the observed variables are acceptable and will be used in the subsequent factor analysis.

5.1.3. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA)

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) for independent variables

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
	KMO	0.846
Bartlett's Test	Approximate chi-square.	1218,700
	DF	91
	Sig value.	0.000

Table 3: The results of the KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) test and Bartlett's test for the independent variable group.

(Source: Results of data processing on SPSS software)

The results of the factor analysis show that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure is 0.846, which is greater than 0.5. This indicates a high degree of model appropriateness.

The Barlett’s Test of Sphericity yields a value of 1218,700, with a significance level (p-value) of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This suggests that the variables are correlated with each other and meet the conditions for factor analysis.

Rotated Component Matrix ^a

	Factor loadings			
	1	2	3	4
LX2	0.893			
LX1	0.886			
LX3	0.822			
LX4	0.821			
LN1		0.892		
LN2		0.830		
LN3		0.823		
LN4		0.797		
CX2			0.845	
CX1			0.843	
CX3			0.824	
CB2				0.877
CB1				0.831
CB3				0.809
Eigenvalue	1,350			
Total variance extracted	78,911			

Table 4: Factor rotation matrix

(Source: Results of processing survey data on SPSS software)

All independent observed variables have factor loadings above 0.6. The results of the factor analysis are consistent with the initial assumptions of the research model.

The total variance extracted is 78,911%, which is greater than the recommended threshold of 50%, indicating that it meets the requirement. The eigenvalues of all factors

are high (>1). These results indicate that the observed variables are correlated with each other in the overall dataset, and the exploratory factor analysis is appropriate.

5.1.4. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) for the dependent variable group

In the research model, the group of dependent variables consists of 6 observed variables, namely BV1, BV2, BV3, BV4, BV5, BV6.

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
KMO		0.876
Bartlett's Test	Approximate Chi-Square	338,003
	Df	15
	Sig value.	0.000

Table 5: The results of the KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) test and Bartlett's test for the dependent variable group

(Source: Results of processing survey data on SPSS software)

The analysis results (Table 5) show that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy is 0.876, indicating that the analyzed data are very suitable for factor analysis and the factor analysis is appropriate. The assumption of correlation between the observed variables included in the analysis is accepted with a Sig. value of the Bartlett's test of 0.000, which is less than 0.05.

Observed variables	Loading coefficients
	1
BV1	0.835
BV2	0.816
BV4	0.809
BV3	0.799
BV5	0.703
BV6	0.694
Eigenvalue	3,631
Total variance extracted	60,518

Table 6: Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) results for the dependent variable group.

(Source: Results of processing survey data on SPSS software)

According to the analysis results (Table 6), the group of 6 observed variables included in the analysis converged and differentiated into 1 factor. The factor loadings of the 6 observed variables are all greater than 0.6, indicating that the group of dependent variables is consistent with the assumption of the research model. The observed variables and the factor group are retained and used for further analysis.

5.1.5. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

(i) Evaluate the model fit through the adjusted R-squared coefficient.

The coefficient of determination R-squared (R^2) is used to assess the goodness-of-fit of the research model. The first step is to check the adequacy of the model.

Model Summary ^b

Model	R	R ²	R ² adjusted	Standard error	Durbin-Watson
First	0.766 ^a	0.586	0.573	0.48843	2,180

Table 7: R2 coefficient (R square)

(Source: SPSS analysis results)

The adjusted R2 coefficient is 0.573, meaning this model explains 57.3% of the variation in the dependent variable (customer satisfaction) through 4 factors of the independent variable. Thus, the research model is appropriate and closely correlated. The results also show that the adjusted R2 is safer than the R2 used to evaluate the fit of the research model because it does not inflate the fit of the model..

ANOVA ^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	42,948	4	10,737	45,007	0.000 ^b
	Residual	30,297	127	0.239		
	Total	73,245	131			

Table 8: Anova test

(Source: SPSS analysis results)

According to the results in Table 4.8, the F-test has a significance value (Sig.) of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H0) is rejected, indicating

that R-squared is not equal to 0 with statistical significance. This implies that the regression model is appropriate. In other words, the model fits the overall data well, and the independent variables in the model can explain the variation in the dependent variable.

5.1.6. Testing research hypotheses

The results of the regression analysis are presented in Table 4. 9.

Coefficients ^a

Model	Unstandardized regression coefficients		Standardized regression coefficient	t	Sig.	Multicollinearity statistics		
	B	Standardized error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	1,027	0.227		4,534	0.000		
	LN	0.188	0.047	0.265	4,005	0.000	0.744	1,344
	CB	0.206	0.047	0.294	4,427	0.000	0.737	1,356
	LX	0.156	0.052	0.198	3,010	0.003	0.756	1,322
	CX	0.184	0.046	0.276	3,972	0.000	0.673	1,485

a. Dependent Variable: BV

Table 9: Results of regression analysis model

(Source: SPSS analysis results)

The accepted regression equation is as follows:

$$BV = 1.027 + 0.188*LN + 0.206CB + 0.156*LX + 0.184*CX$$

The results of the standardized regression coefficients analysis indicate that the independent factors have varying degrees of influence on the dependent variable. The influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable ranks in descending order as follows: Carbon emission management > Green transportation practices > Reverse Logistics practices > Green fuel use practices.

5.2. Conclusion

Research on the impact of green Logistics practices on the sustainable efficiency of businesses providing Logistics services is an important step in understanding and promoting sustainable development in the Logistics industry. The study results showed that the four factors of green Logistics practices: reverse Logistics practices, carbon emission management, green fuel usage practices, and green transportation practices have a close connection and support each other. Therefore, to improve sustainable efficiency, Logistics service providers should apply methods to implement green Logistics activities.

First, reduce carbon emissions. As a major greenhouse gas emitting industry, Logistics enterprises need to join hands to repel climate change. Businesses can optimize transportation, save fuel, use environmentally friendly packaging, and switch to renewable energy. This is not only a responsibility but also an inevitable trend for businesses to survive and develop sustainably in the future.

Second, greening transportation activities. This is the Foundation for Sustainable Logistics. Businesses investing in vehicles that meet emission standards, applying technology to optimize journeys, and using effective transport management software are practical solutions to greening transport activities. This reduces environmental pollution, improves operational efficiency, and saves business costs.

Finally, the application operates Reverse Logistics. Reverse Logistics plays an important role in recovering, reusing, and recycling products, contributing to reducing waste and saving resources. Enterprises need to build an effective goods recall system, speed up the processing of return requests, and apply a modern recall information system. Reverse Logistics not only benefits the environment but also helps businesses improve service quality, increase competitive advantage, and strengthen "green" brand image.

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